

NON-ABELIAN AFFINE GROUPS WITH SCALAR LINEAR PART ACTING ON \mathbb{R}^n

ADLENE AYADI, YAHIA N'DAO AND HAMED BEN YAHIA

ABSTRACT. In this paper, we explore the action of a non-Abelian group G on \mathbb{R}^n , where G consists of affine transformations with linear parts being scalar multiples of the identity matrix. We provide a complete criterion for when G admits a dense orbit, thus characterizing its hypercyclic behavior. Additionally, we present an explicit and unified description of the closure of any orbit under the group action.

Specifically, we express the closure of an orbit passing through any point $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ as: $\overline{G(x)} = \Lambda \cdot T_x(K)$, where Λ is a multiplicative subgroup of $\mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$, and K is an additive subgroup invariant under Λ . This form reveals a structure that partially mirrors the symmetry seen in Abelian group actions. The results offer a framework that can be extended to a broader class of non-Abelian affine groups.

1. INTRODUCTION

An affine map on \mathbb{R}^n is a transformation of the form:

$$f(x) = Ax + b$$

where A is an invertible matrix with real coefficients and $b \in \mathbb{R}^n$. The matrix A is called the linear part of f and b the translation vector of f or $b = f(0)$. Affine maps are essential in mathematics, including ergodic theory, geometry, and physics such as in mechanics, relativity, and quantum theory. They also play a key role in robotics, computer vision, and various other fields [7], [8].

In [11] and [12], the authors studied the topological dynamics of the abelian case of affine and linear groups acting on \mathbb{K}^n , $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R}$ or \mathbb{C} . They demonstrate that every orbit is locally diffeomorphic to an additive subgroup of \mathbb{K}^n , reflecting the orbit of the translation group on \mathbb{K}^n . This result does not extend to the non-abelian case, because the lack of symmetry of non-abelian transformations blocks the application of these tools. When $A = \lambda I_n$, with $\lambda \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ and I_n being the identity matrix of order n , we say that the affine map f has a scalar linear part, so it is an affine homothety or a translation. Since homothety is the simplest non-abelian case,

2000 *Mathematics Subject Classification.* 37C85.

Key words and phrases. Non abelian, affine, group, Action, dilations, Homothety, transformations, translations, rotation, dense orbit, hypercyclic.

This work is supported by the research unit: systèmes dynamiques et combinatoire: 99UR15-15.

this work aims to study the dynamics of non-abelian groups generated by homotheties, thus providing a basis for addressing the more general affine case and understanding the complexity of non-abelian group actions.

2. AFFINE GROUPS WITH SCALAR LINEAR PART

The set of affine transformations $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, defined by $f(x) = \lambda x + b$ for a nonzero real λ and a given vector $b \in \mathbb{R}^n$ can be classified into two categories: translations and homotheties. Translations are those with $\lambda = 1$, and homotheties are those with $\lambda \neq 1$. Homotheties are determined by a center point $a = b/(1 - \lambda)$ and a ratio λ . In what follows, we will denote a homothety h with center a and ratio λ as (λ, a) . It can be defined as $h = T_a \circ \lambda \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n} \circ T_{-a}$, where T_a is the translation by the vector $a \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}$ is the identity map of \mathbb{R}^n .

The set of all such transformations, known as the *dilations group* [13, p. 40] or the *homotheties and translations group*, is denoted by $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. Specifically,

$$\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R}) := \{f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n \mid x \mapsto \lambda x + b, \lambda \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\} \text{ and } b \in \mathbb{R}^n\}.$$

It forms a non-abelian group under the composition of mappings. The group action of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$ on \mathbb{R}^n is defined as follows: for $f \in \mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $(f, x) \mapsto f(x)$.

An affine group with scalar linear part is every subgroup G of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$.

Note that every element f of the dilations group can be written as either a homothety (λ, a) or a translation T_a . If $f = (\lambda, a)$, then for every integer m , we have

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \lambda(x - a) + a & \text{if } \lambda \neq 1 \\ x + a & \text{if } \lambda = 1 \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad f^m(x) = \begin{cases} \lambda^m(x - a) + a & \text{if } \lambda \neq 1 \\ x + ma & \text{if } \lambda = 1 \end{cases}$$

However, if we write f in the general form $f(x) = \lambda x + b$, which is valid for both homotheties and translations, we cannot use this form for f^m because in general, $f^m(x) \neq \lambda^m x + b$. This means that $f(0) \neq f^m(0)$ in general. Additionally, we will denote any translation T_a by $(1, a)$. This means that if $f = (\lambda, a)$, then:

$$f(a) = a \quad \text{if } \lambda \neq 1 \quad \text{and} \quad f(0) = a \quad \text{if } \lambda = 1$$

The orbit of a vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ under the action of a non-abelian subgroup G of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$, denoted as $G(x) = \{y \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \exists f \in G \text{ such that } y = f(x)\}$. A group G is said to be hypercyclic if it has a dense orbit. A dilation $f \in \mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$, defined as $f(x) = \lambda x + b$, has a scalar linear part given by the map $x \mapsto \lambda x$.

A subset $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is called G -invariant if $f(E) \subset E$ under any element f of G . The closure of a set E is denoted \overline{E} . A group G is considered minimal if all its orbits are dense in \mathbb{R}^n , and it is said to be minimal within a G -invariant open set U if $\overline{G(x)} \cap U = U$ for all $x \in U$.

In this paper, we are interested in characterizing the hypercyclicity and minimality of non-abelian subgroups of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. In previous work, such as [17] and [14], the authors studied the semigroup of affine transformations of \mathbb{R} and proved strong density results for the orbits of the real numbers under the action of certain semigroups generated by affine transformations.

Consider a non-abelian group G generated by homotheties acting on \mathbb{R}^n . We show that the closure of an orbit O can be expressed by

$$\overline{O} = T_b(\overline{\Lambda a + K}),$$

where Λ is a multiplicative subgroup of $\mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$, K is an additive subgroup of \mathbb{R}^n , and $a, b \in \mathbb{R}^n$. This form is not generally invariant under summation or multiplication.

Studying the density of sets having the form $\Lambda \cdot a + K$ can be quite tricky, even in the one-dimensional case, because it is often related to questions about the distribution of fractional parts of geometric sequences in $[0, 1]$ ([15], [16]). This form reflects non-Abelian behavior, where its closure deviates from familiar linear or multiplicative models. In this work, the multiplicative group Λ and the additive group K interact through the action of a group G , satisfying in particular the relation $\Lambda \cdot K = K$. This compatibility allows us to considerably simplify the expression $\Lambda \cdot a + K$. This leads to two situations: on the one hand, if the closure of K is a vector space, the structure behaves more regularly; on the other hand, when this is not the case, the group Λ must necessarily be finite. In the latter case, we avoid the complex phenomena associated with the distribution of fractional parts that arise in classical multiplicative dynamics.

Under these assumptions, we can describe the closure of any orbit O of a point $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ as:

$$\overline{O} = \overline{\Lambda} \cdot T_x(K).$$

where T_x is the translation by x . This expression has a simpler structure: it resembles that of a closed additive group, but with an initial translation followed by a multiplication by the closure of a multiplicative group. This results in a form of partial symmetry, close to what one might expect in the abelian case. Our broader goal is to generalize this structure to encompass all actions of non-abelian affine groups.

In this paper, we will use the following notations:

- $\mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R}) := \{f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n \mid x \mapsto \lambda x + b, \lambda \in \{-1, 1\} \text{ and } b \in \mathbb{R}^n\}$ is the set of all translations and point symmetries of \mathbb{R}^n . It is easy to see that $\mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R})$ is a subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$.

Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. We denote:

- $G_s = \{f = (\lambda, a) \in G; |\lambda| = 1\}$ is the set of dilations of G that are a translation or a point symmetry. Note that $G_s = G \cap \mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R})$.
- $\mathcal{T}(n, \mathbb{R})$ is the set of all translations of \mathbb{R}^n .

- $G_t = G \cap \mathcal{T}(n, \mathbb{R})$ is the subgroup of all translations of G . Since G is not abelian, $G \setminus G_t$ is always nonempty.
- $G_t(0) = \{T(0) \mid T \in G_t\}$, the orbit of 0 under the action of G_t , which is the additive group of all translation vectors of G_t .
- $\Lambda_G = \{\lambda : f = (\lambda, a) \in G\}$ is the collection of all ratios of any element $f \in G$. It is a multiplicative subgroup of $\mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$.
- $\text{Fix}(f) = \{a \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid f(a) = a\}$, the center of a dilation $f = (\lambda, a) \in \mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R}) \setminus G \cap \mathcal{T}(n, \mathbb{R})$ or the empty set if f is a translation.
- $C_t(G) = \bigcup_{f \in G \setminus G_t} \text{Fix}(f)$, the set of centers of all homotheties and point symmetries of $G \setminus G_t$. It is called the center of G .

Our principal results are the following:

Theorem 2.1. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. Then there exists $a \in C_t(G)$ such that for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$,*

$$\overline{G(x)} = T_a \left(\overline{\Lambda_G(x - a) + G_t(0)} \right).$$

where T_a is the translation by vector a .

For such non abelian group G , we denote:

- $E_G = \text{Aff}(C_t(G))$, the smallest \mathbb{R} -affine subspace of \mathbb{R}^n containing $C_t(G)$.
- $U = \mathbb{R}^n \setminus E_G$ the open set which is dense in \mathbb{R}^n when it is nonempty.
- $\text{Vect}(E)$, the smallest vector space containing any subset E of \mathbb{R}^n .

Denote by T_y is the translation by vector y . We have:

Corollary 2.2. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. Then there exists $a \in C_t(G)$ such that for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$,*

$$\overline{G(x)} = T_a \left(\overline{\Lambda_G((x - a) + G_t(0))} \right).$$

More over, if $0 \in C_t(G)$ then

$$\overline{G(x)} = \overline{\Lambda_G} \cdot T_x \left(\overline{G_t(0)} \right).$$

Theorem 2.3. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$.*

(1) *If $G \setminus G_s$ is nonempty, then:*

- (i) $\overline{G(x)} = \overline{G_t(0)} = E_G$, for every $x \in E_G$.
- (ii) *There exists an element $a \in E_G$ such that for every $x \in U$,*

$$\overline{G(x)} = \overline{\Lambda_G}(x - a) + E_G.$$

(2) *If $G = G_s$, then there exists an element $a \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$,*

$$\overline{G(x)} = \left(x + \overline{G_t(0)} \right) \cup \left(-x + a + \overline{G_t(0)} \right).$$

We give a complete criterion so that G is hypercyclic :

Theorem 2.4. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. Then the following statements are equivalent:*

- (a) G is hypercyclic.
- (b) G satisfies one of the following:
 - (i) $E_G = \mathbb{R}^n$.
 - (ii) $G \setminus G_s \neq \emptyset$, $\dim_{\mathbb{R}}(E_G) = n - 1$ and $\overline{\Lambda_G} = \mathbb{R}$.
 - (iii) $G = G_s$ and $\overline{G_t(0)} = \mathbb{R}^n$.

The following corollaries are straightforward results from the previous theorems

Theorem 2.5. *Let G be an hypercyclic, non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$ such that $E_G \neq \mathbb{R}^n$. Then G is minimal in U , and every orbit of U is dense in \mathbb{R}^n .*

3. GENERAL PROPERTIES OF NON-ABELIAN SUBGROUPS IN $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$

Let G be a non abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$, denote by:

- $C_s(G) = \bigcup_{f \in G \setminus G_s} \text{Fix}(f)$, the set of centers of all dilations of $G \setminus G_s$. Note

that $C_s(G) = \{a \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \text{there exists } f = (\lambda, a) \in G \text{ with } |\lambda| \neq 1\}$. It is called the center of $G \setminus G_s$.

Lemma 3.1. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. Then for every $f = (\lambda, a) \in G \setminus G_t$, $T_{-a} \circ f \circ T_a = \lambda \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}$. Moreover, $G' = T_{-a} G T_a$ is a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$ and its center contains zero.*

Proof. It is easy to verify that $T_{-a} \circ f \circ T_a = \lambda \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n} \in G'$ for every $f = (\lambda, a) \in G \setminus G_t$. Therefore, the center $C_s(G')$ of G' contains zero. \square

Lemma 3.2. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$, and let $a \in E_G$. Then the group $G' = T_{-a} \circ G \circ T_a$ satisfies $0 \in \Lambda_{G'}$, $\Lambda_{G'} = \Lambda_G$, $C_s(G) = C_s(G') + a$, $E_G = E_{G'} + a$, $G_t(0) = T_a(G'_t(0))$ and $U = U' + a$, where $U' = \mathbb{R}^n \setminus E_{G'}$.*

The proof is obvious because $T_{-a} \circ g \circ T_a = (\mu, T_{-a}(b))$ if $g = (\mu, b)$, $C_s(G) = T_a(C_s(G'))$, $G_t(0) = T_a(G'_t(0))$ and $E_G = T_a(E_{G'})$.

Lemma 3.3. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. Then:*

- i) $G_t(0)$ is a non-trivial additive group.
- ii) $G \setminus G_t$ is not empty.
- iii) There is a ratio other than 1 in Λ_G .
- iv) $G_t(0) = \Lambda_G G_t(0)$.
- v) $C_t(G)$ is a nonempty set.

Proof. i) Notice that $G_t(0)$ contains zero because G_t contains the identity map of \mathbb{R}^n . Let $f = (\lambda, a)$ and $g = (\mu, b)$ be two homotheties in G that do not commute. We can check that $f \circ g \circ f^{-1} = h = (\mu, f(b))$, and by a simple computation, we get $T = f \circ g \circ f^{-1} \circ g^{-1} = h \circ g^{-1}$. Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} T(x) &= \mu \left(\frac{1}{\mu}(x - b) + b - f(b) \right) + f(b) \\ &= x + (\mu - 1)(b - f(b)) \\ &= T_c \end{aligned}$$

with $c = (\mu - 1)(b - f(b))$ is a non-null vector since $f(b)$ is distinct from b , because f and g do not commute. Hence T is a non-trivial translation in G .

ii) The result follows from the fact that G_t is abelian but G is not.

iii) The proof follows directly from i) and ii).

iv) Let $\mu \in \Lambda_G \setminus \{1\}$ and $b \in G_t(0)$. Consider the dilation $f = (\mu, a) \in G \setminus G_t$ with ratio μ . Using the composition $f \circ T_b \circ f^{-1}(x) = x + \mu b$, we prove that μb is a translation vector contained in $G_t(0)$. The converse is obvious by iii), so $\Lambda_G.G_t(0) = G_t(0)$.

v) If $C_t(G)$ is empty, then G consists only of translations, so $G = G_t$ which contradicts ii). \square

4. G CONTAINS ELEMENTS OTHER THAN TRANSLATIONS AND POINT SYMMETRIES

($G \setminus G_s \neq \emptyset$)

In this section, we consider the case where G is a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$ that has at least one dilation $f = (\lambda, a)$ with $|\lambda| \neq 1$. Our goal is to prove that $\overline{G_t(0)}$ cannot be a discrete additive group contained in the closure of any orbit of G .

Lemma 4.1. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. Then the set Λ_G is a multiplicative subgroup of $\mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$. Furthermore, if $G \setminus G_s$ is nonempty, then the closure $\overline{\Lambda_G}$ of Λ_G contains zero.*

Proof. It is easy to verify that Λ_G forms a multiplicative subgroup of $\mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$. If G_s is non-empty, it must contain a dilation of the form $f = (\lambda, a)$ where $|\lambda| < 1$. This implies that the sequence of powers λ^m for large m approaches zero. Therefore, it follows that the closure of Λ_G , denoted by $\overline{\Lambda_G}$, contains the point zero. \square

Lemma 4.2. ([18], Theorem 3.1) *Let K be a closed additive subgroup of \mathbb{R}^n . If K is not a vector space, then there exist positive integers p and r with $0 \leq p+r \leq n$ and a basis (b_1, \dots, b_n) of \mathbb{R}^n such that $K = \sum_{k=1}^p \mathbb{R}b_k + \sum_{k=p+1}^{p+r} \mathbb{Z}b_k$ where $r \geq 1$.*

Lemma 4.3. *Let G be a non abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$ such that $G \setminus G_s$ is nonempty. Then:*

- (i) $C_s(G)$ is G -invariant.
- (ii) If $C_s(G)$ contains zero, the closures of $G(0)$, $G_t(0)$, and $C_s(G)$ are all equal to E_G . In particular, they are vector spaces and G -invariant.

Proof. First, we observe that since $C_s(G)$ contains zero, then $G \setminus G_s$ must contain dilations of the form $h = \lambda \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}$ where either $|\lambda| \neq 1$. Without loss of generality, we can assume that there exists a dilation $h = \lambda \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}$ with $|\lambda| > 1$, otherwise, we take the inverse.

(i) To prove that $C_s(G)$ is invariant under the action of G , consider an element $a \in C_s(G)$ and an element $g \in G$. Take a dilation $f \in G_s$ with center a . Since $g \circ f \circ g^{-1}$ is also in $G \setminus G_s$, it follows that the center of $g \circ f \circ g^{-1}$, which is $g(a)$, is also in $C_s(G)$. Therefore, $C_s(G)$ is invariant under the action of G .

(ii) \diamond To show that $\overline{G_t(0)}$ is a vector space, we suppose the converse. If this were the case, then $\overline{G_t(0)}$ would be a closed additive subgroup of \mathbb{R}^n . According to Lemma 4.2, this means that $\overline{G_t(0)}$ can be expressed as follow

$$\overline{G_t(0)} = \sum_{k=1}^p \mathbb{R}b_k \oplus H',$$

where $H' = \sum_{k=p+1}^{p+r} \mathbb{Z}b_k$, (b_1, \dots, b_n) is a basis of \mathbb{R}^n and p, r are positive integers such that $0 \leq p+r \leq n$, $r \geq 1$.

We let $c = \inf \left\{ \|u\|; u \in \overline{G_t(0)} \text{ and } u \notin \sum_{k=1}^p \mathbb{R}b_k \right\}$. As $H' \setminus \{0\}$ is contained in H' which is a closed and discrete group, we know that $c > 0$. We consider the dilation $h = \lambda \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}$ where $\lambda > 1$. By choosing m sufficiently large, we can ensure that $\|\lambda^{-m} b_{p+1}\| < c$ for all $m \geq m_0$ for some m_0 . This means that $\|h^{-m}(b_{p+1})\| < c$ and, as a result, $h^{-m}(b_{p+1}) \notin \overline{G_t(0)}$. On the other hand, by Lemma 3.3.iv), $G_t(0) = \Lambda_G G_t(0)$ then $G_t(0)$ is h -invariant, and so $\overline{G_t(0)}$ is also h -invariant. This leads to the conclusion that $\lambda^{-m} b_{p+1} \in \overline{G_t(0)}$, which is a contradiction. Thus, $\overline{G_t(0)}$ must be a vector space.

\diamond To prove that $\overline{C_s(G)} = \overline{G_t(0)}$, we show that $C_s(G) \subseteq \overline{G_t(0)}$ and $G_t(0) \subseteq \overline{C_s(G)}$. Let $b \in C_s(G)$. Then there exists $g = (b, \mu) \in G_s$. We know that

$g \circ h \circ g^{-1} \circ h^{-1} = T_{(\lambda-1)(\mu-1)b}$, which means that $(\lambda-1)(\mu-1)b \in G_t(0)$. Since $\overline{G_t(0)}$ is a vector space, we can divide by $(\lambda-1)(\mu-1)$, which is non-zero, to obtain $b \in \overline{G_t(0)}$. On the other hand, let $b \in G_t(0)$. Then the dilation $T_b \circ h \circ T_{-b} = (\lambda, b) \in G \setminus G_s$, so $b \in C_s(G)$. Therefore, $C_s(G) = \overline{G_t(0)}$.

◊ To prove that $E_G = \overline{C_s(G)}$, we first note that $C_s(G)$ contains zero, so E_G is the smallest vector space containing $C_s(G)$. We also know from the above step that $\overline{G_t(0)}$ is a vector space, and from the previous result, $C_s(G) = \overline{G_t(0)}$. Therefore, $E_G = \overline{C_s(G)}$.

◊ Finally, we show that $\overline{G(0)} = E_G$. By (i), $C_s(G)$ is G -invariant and contains zero, so its orbit $G(0)$ is also contained in $C_s(G)$. Therefore, $\overline{G(0)} \subset \overline{C_s(G)} = E_G$, which, combined with the fact that $E_G \subset \overline{G(0)}$, implies that $\overline{G(0)} = E_G$. This completes the proof. \square

Proposition 4.4. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup G of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. Suppose that $G \setminus G_s$ is nonempty, then the closure of every orbit of G contains $C_s(G)$. Additionally, if $C_s(G)$ contains zero, then any orbit in E_G is dense there. (i.e. $\overline{G(x)} = E_G$ for every $x \in E_G$).*

Proof. In this proof, we aim to show that (i) every orbit of G contains $C_s(G)$ in its closure, and (ii) when $C_s(G)$ contains zero, $\overline{G(x)} = E_G$ for all $x \in E_G$.

To prove (i), we consider an element $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, and an element $a \in C_s(G)$. We choose a dilation $f = (\lambda, a)$, with center a and some ratio λ such that $|\lambda| \neq 1$. Without loss of generality, we assume that $|\lambda| < 1$ (we can always take the inverse if necessary). Since $f^k(x) = \lambda^k(x - a) + a$ approaches a as $k \rightarrow +\infty$, it follows that $a \in \overline{G(x)}$.

For (ii), we use the fact that E_G is a vector space (shown in Lemma 4.3.ii), and consider an element $x \in E_G$. By (i), we have that $C_s(G) \subset \overline{G(x)}$, and by Lemma 4.3.(ii), $E_G = \overline{C_s(G)}$, so E_G is contained in $\overline{G(x)}$. Since E_G is G -invariant (Lemma 4.3, (ii)), we also have that $\overline{G(x)} \subset E_G$, which implies that $\overline{G(x)} = E_G$. This completes the proof. \square

Recall that $U = \mathbb{R}^n \setminus E_G$ is an open set which is G -invariant if $C_s(G)$ contains zero (as E_G is G -invariant, see Lemma 4.3). When U is nonempty, we will determine the closure of all its orbits.

Proposition 4.5. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. Suppose that $C_s(G)$ contains zero and the set $U = \mathbb{R}^n \setminus E_G$ is not empty. Then for every $x \in U$, $\overline{G(x)} = \Lambda_G \cdot x + E_G$.*

Proof. Let $x \in U$ and consider an element $\lambda \in \overline{\Lambda_G}$ and an element $b \in E_G$. We can find a sequence $(\lambda_m)_m$ in Λ_G that converges to λ . For each positive integer m , we can also find a dilation $f_m \in G$ of the form $f_m : x \mapsto \lambda_m x + b_m$, where $b_m \in G(0)$. Since $C_s(G)$ contains zero, $\overline{G_t(0)} = \overline{G(0)} = E_G$ by Lemma 4.3.(ii). Therefore, $b, b_m \in \overline{G_t(0)}$ and so $b - b_m \in \overline{G_t(0)}$. We can then find a sequence $(c_{m_k})_k$ in $G_t(0)$ such that $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} c_{m_k} = b - b_m$. This allows us to write:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_m x + b &= f_m(x) + (b - b_m) \\ &= \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (f_m(x) + c_{m_k}) \\ &= \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (T_{c_{m_k}} \circ f_m(x)) \end{aligned}$$

It follows that $\lambda_m x + b \in \overline{G(z)}$ for every m . This means that $\lambda x + b = \lim_{m \rightarrow +\infty} (\lambda_m x + b) \in \overline{G(x)}$. This is true for every $\lambda \in \overline{\Lambda_G}$ and $b \in E_G$, so we can conclude that $\overline{\Lambda_G} \cdot x + E_G$ is contained in the closure of $G(x)$. To prove the converse, let $f \in G$ be an element of the group. Then we have $f(x) = \lambda x + f(0)$ for some $\lambda \in \overline{\Lambda_G}$ and $f(0) \in E_G$. Since $\overline{G(0)} = E_G$ by Lemma 4.3.(ii), it follows that $f(x) \in \overline{\Lambda_G} \cdot x + E_G$. As a result, $\overline{\Lambda_G} \cdot x + E_G$ is a closed set containing $G(x)$. We conclude that $\overline{G(x)} = \overline{\Lambda_G} \cdot x + E_G$ for every x in U . \square

Remark 4.6. In the case where G is a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$ with a nonempty set of scaling transformations G_s , it follows that $\overline{\Lambda_G}$ includes zero and E_G is an affine, G -invariant subspace of \mathbb{R}^n with a dimension of at least 1.

Proof. Firstly, we know that $C_s(G)$ is not empty since $G \setminus G_s$ is not empty. By Lemma 4.1, the closure of Λ_G contains zero. Additionally, by Lemma 4.3.(ii), E_G is G -invariant and $\overline{G(0)} = E_G$. Since G is non-abelian, the orbit $G(0)$ cannot be reduced to the single point 0. This is because the identity map $\text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}$ and the homotheties with center 0 are the only elements of G that fix 0 and they commute. Therefore, we deduce that the dimension of E_G must be greater or equal than 1. \square

5. G IS A NON-ABELIEN SUBGROUP OF $\mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R})$

In this section, every transformation f in the group G is either a translation or a point symmetry of the form $f : y \mapsto \varepsilon y + b$, where $|\varepsilon| = 1$. The set Λ_G consists of the two possible values for ε , namely, -1 and 1 .

Lemma 5.1. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R})$. Then there exists a point $a \in G(0) \setminus G_t(0)$ such that for any point $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $\overline{G(x)} = \left(x + \overline{G_t(0)}\right) \cup \left(-x + a + \overline{G_t(0)}\right)$.*

Proof. Since G is non-abelian, it contains elements that are not in G_t , so let us fix an element $a \in G(0) \setminus G_t(0)$ and choose $S \in G \setminus G_t$ such that $S : y \mapsto -y + a$. We observe that $G_t(x) \cup S(G_t(x)) = (x + G_t(0)) \cup (-x + a + G_t(0))$, which is contained in the orbit of x under G . Therefore, its closure $\left(x + \overline{G_t(0)}\right) \cup \left(-x + a + \overline{G_t(0)}\right)$ is contained in the closure $\overline{G(x)}$ of the orbit $G(x)$.

To prove the converse, consider any $f \in G$ given by $f : y \mapsto \varepsilon y + b$ where $|\varepsilon| = 1$. If $\varepsilon = 1$, then $f(x) = x + b$ is contained in $x + \overline{G_t(0)}$. If $\varepsilon = -1$, then $f(x) = -x + b = -x + a + (b - a)$. Since $S(f(x)) = x + b - a$, we get $b - a \in G_t(0)$. This means that $f(x)$ is contained in $-x + a + \overline{G_t(0)}$. Therefore, every element of $G(x)$ is contained in either $x + \overline{G_t(0)}$ or $-x + a + \overline{G_t(0)}$, which means that the closure of the orbit $G(x)$ is contained in $\left(x + \overline{G_t(0)}\right) \cup \left(-x + a + \overline{G_t(0)}\right)$. Thus, the proof is complete. \square

6. PROOF OF MAIN RESULTS

Proof of Theorem 2.1. We proceed by considering two distinct cases:

Case 1: Suppose that $G \setminus G_s$ is nonempty, then so is $C_s(G)$. Without loss of generality, we may assume that $0 \in C_s(G)$. This can be ensured by conjugating G via $T_{-a}GT_a$ for some $a \in C_s(G)$. Under this assumption, by Lemma 4.3, the space E_G becomes a vector space.

Let $x \in E_G$ be arbitrary. By Proposition 4.4, we have:

$$\overline{G(x)} = E_G = \Lambda_G \cdot x + E_G,$$

since $\Lambda_G \cdot x \subset E_G$. Furthermore, by Lemma 4.3, we also know that $\overline{G_t(0)} = E_G$. Hence, it follows that:

$$\overline{G(x)} = \overline{\Lambda_G \cdot x + G_t(0)}.$$

Now, for any $x \in U$, Proposition 4.5 gives:

$$\overline{G(x)} = \overline{\Lambda_G \cdot x + E_G}.$$

Using again that $E_G = \overline{G_t(0)}$ and $x \notin E_G$, we conclude:

$$\overline{G(x)} = \overline{\Lambda_G \cdot x + G_t(0)} = \overline{\Lambda_G \cdot x + \overline{G_t(0)}},$$

which establishes the result when $a = 0$.

Case 2: Assume now that $G \setminus G_s = \emptyset$, so that $G \subset \mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R})$. Then, by

Lemma 5.1, there exists a point $b \in G(0) \setminus G_t(0)$ such that for any point $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, we have

$$\overline{G(x)} = \left(x + \overline{G_t(0)}\right) \cup \left(-x + b + \overline{G_t(0)}\right).$$

In this case, $\Lambda_G = \{-1, 1\}$, because G is non-abelian, and thus necessarily contains a point symmetry $S : x \mapsto -x + b$; otherwise, it would be a group of translations, which is abelian. We deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{G(x)} &= T_{\frac{b}{2}} \left(\left(x - \frac{b}{2} + \overline{G_t(0)}\right) \cup \left(-x + \frac{b}{2} + \overline{G_t(0)}\right) \right) \\ &= T_{\frac{b}{2}} \left(\overline{\Lambda_G \cdot \left(x - \frac{b}{2} + G_t(0)\right)} \right) \\ &= T_a \left(\overline{\Lambda_G \cdot (x - a + G_t(0))} \right) \end{aligned}$$

where $a = \frac{b}{2} \in C_t(G)$. □

Proof of Corollary 2.2. Let $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$. We consider two distinct cases:

Case 1: Assume that $G \setminus G_s \neq \emptyset$. In this case, $C_s(G)$ is also nonempty. By Lemma 3.3.iv), we have $G_t(0) = \Lambda_G G_t(0)$. Then, by Theorem 2.1, there exists some $a \in C_t(G)$ such that

$$\overline{G(x)} = T_a \left(\overline{\Lambda_G \cdot (x - a) + G_t(0)} \right) = T_a \left(\overline{\Lambda_G \cdot (x - a) + \Lambda_G \cdot G_t(0)} \right).$$

Next, observe that

$$\Lambda_G \cdot (x - a + G_t(0)) \subset \Lambda_G \cdot (x - a) + \Lambda_G \cdot G_t(0).$$

For the reverse inclusion, let $y = \lambda \cdot (x - a) + \mu \cdot b$, where $\lambda, \mu \in \Lambda$ and $b \in G_t(0)$. We can express $\mu \cdot b = \lambda \cdot (\lambda^{-1} \mu \cdot b)$, and by Lemma 3.3.iv), we have $c = \lambda^{-1} \mu \cdot b \in G_t(0)$. Thus, we can write

$$y = \lambda \cdot (x - a + c) \in \Lambda_G \cdot (x - a + G_t(0)).$$

Therefore, we conclude that

$$\Lambda_G \cdot (x - a + G_t(0)) = \Lambda_G \cdot (x - a) + \Lambda_G \cdot G_t(0).$$

Thus, we obtain

$$\overline{G(x)} = T_a \left(\overline{\Lambda_G \cdot (x - a + G_t(0))} \right).$$

Case 2: Now, assume that $G \setminus G_s = \emptyset$, so that $G \subset \mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R})$. In this case, we have $\Lambda_G = \{-1, 1\}$. By Lemma 5.1, there exists $b \in G(0) \setminus G_t(0)$ such that for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, we can write

$$\overline{G(x)} = \left(x + \overline{G_t(0)}\right) \cup \left(-x + b + \overline{G_t(0)}\right).$$

By applying the translation $T_{\frac{b}{2}}$, we get

$$\overline{G(x)} = T_{\frac{b}{2}} \left(\left(x - \frac{b}{2} + \overline{G_t(0)} \right) \cup \left(-x + \frac{b}{2} + \overline{G_t(0)} \right) \right),$$

which simplifies to

$$\overline{G(x)} = T_{\frac{b}{2}} \left(\Lambda_G \cdot \left(x - \frac{b}{2} + \overline{G_t(0)} \right) \right).$$

Thus, we have

$$\overline{G(x)} = T_{\frac{b}{2}} \left(\overline{\Lambda_G \cdot \left(x - \frac{b}{2} + \overline{G_t(0)} \right)} \right).$$

Finally, we take $a = \frac{b}{2}$. Since $b \in G(0) \setminus G_t(0)$ then $a \in \text{Fix}(S) \subset C_t(G)$. We deduce that

$$\overline{G(x)} = T_a \left(\overline{\Lambda_G \cdot (x - a + \overline{G_t(0)})} \right).$$

If $0 \in C_t(G)$, we obtain the desired result for $a = 0$. \square

Proof of Theorem 2.3. In order to prove that E_G is a vector space, we may assume without loss of generality that $C_s(G)$ contains zero by applying the transformation $T_{-a} \circ G \circ T_a$ for some $a \in E_G$, as stated in Lemma 3.2. This allows us to conclude that E_G is indeed a vector space.

\triangleright To prove statement (1)(i), we can use Proposition 4.4 and Lemma 4.3. Specifically, we can use the fact that if $G \setminus G_s$ is nonempty, then the closure of any orbit $G(x)$ for $x \in E_G$ is equal to E_G . Additionally, we know that $\overline{G_t(0)} = E_G$. Therefore, statement (1)(i) follows directly from these two results.

\triangleright The proof of (1).(ii) of Theorem 2.3 follows from Proposition 4.5, which states that for any point $x \in U$, the closure of its orbit under the action of G is equal to the sum of $\overline{\Lambda_G x}$ and E_G .

\triangleright The proof of (2) of Theorem 2.3 follows directly from Lemma 5.1. \square

Corollary 6.1. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$ such that $E_G \neq \mathbb{R}^n$. Then for every $x \in U$ and $y \in \overline{G(x)} \cap U$, we have $G(x) = G(y)$.*

Proof. Consider the case where E_G is a vector space (we can replace G with $G' = T_{-a} \circ G \circ T_a$ for some $a \in E_G$). Let $x \in U$ and $y \in \overline{G(x)} \cap U$. There are two possibilities:

- $G \setminus G_s$ is not empty: By Theorem 2.3, there exists $a \in E_G$ such that

$\overline{G(x)} = \overline{\Lambda_G}(x - a) + E_G$. Since E_G is a vector space and $a \in E_G$, then $\overline{G(x)} = \overline{\Lambda_G}x + E_G$. In the same way,

$$\overline{G(y)} = \overline{\Lambda_G}y + E_G, \quad (1).$$

See that $\overline{G(x)} \cap U = (\overline{\Lambda_G} \setminus \{0\})x + E_G$. Write $y = \alpha x + b$, where $\alpha \in \overline{\Lambda_G} \setminus \{0\}$ and $b \in E_G$. Since Λ_G is a subgroup of $\mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ and α is nonzero, then $\alpha \overline{\Lambda_G} = \overline{\Lambda_G}$. Therefore, by equation (1), $\overline{G(y)} = \overline{\Lambda_G}(\alpha x + b) + E_G = \overline{\Lambda_G}x + E_G$, since $b \in E_G$. It follows that $\overline{G(y)} = \overline{G(x)}$.

- $G = G_s$: By Lemma 5.1, there exists $a \in G(0) \setminus G_t(0)$ such that $\overline{G(x)} = (x + \overline{G_t(0)}) \cup (-x + a + \overline{G_t(0)})$. If $y \in \overline{G(x)} \cap U$, then there is $b \in \overline{G_t(0)}$ such that $y = x + b$ or $y = -x + a + b$. It follows that $\overline{G(y)} = \overline{G(x)}$.

In both cases, we have shown that $\overline{G(y)} = \overline{G(x)}$. □

Proof of the Theorem 2.4. Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. By Lemma 3.2, suppose that $C_s(G)$ contains zero and thus E_G is a vector subspace of \mathbb{R}^n (we can replace G by $T_{-a} \circ G \circ T_a$, for some $a \in E_G$, if necessary). Then:

◦ (b)(i) \implies (a): If $E_G = \mathbb{R}^n$ and $G \setminus G_s$ is not empty, then by Theorem 2.3.(1).(i), $\overline{G(x)} = E_G$ for every $x \in E_G$. Thus, G is hypercyclic.

◦ (b)(ii) \implies (a): If Λ_G is dense in \mathbb{R} , $\dim(E_G) = n - 1$, and $G \setminus G_s$ is not empty, then by Theorem 2.3.(1).(ii), for every $x \in U = \mathbb{R}^n \setminus E_G$, we have $\overline{G(x)} = \overline{\Lambda_G}x + E_G = \mathbb{R}x + E_G = \mathbb{R}^n$. Therefore, G is hypercyclic.

◦ (b)(iii) \implies (a): By Theorem 2.3.(2), for every $z \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$\overline{G(x)} = \left(x + \overline{G_t(0)} \right) \cup \left(-x + a + \overline{G_t(0)} \right)$$

for some $a \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Thus, if $G_s = \emptyset$ and $\overline{G_t(0)} = \mathbb{R}^n$, G is hypercyclic.

◦ (a) \implies (b): If G is hypercyclic, it has a dense orbit $G(x)$ for some $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$. There are two cases to consider:

▷ *Case 1:* If $E_G = \mathbb{R}^n$, then (b)(i) holds.

▷ *Case 2:* If E_G is distinct from \mathbb{R}^n , then either (b)(ii) or (b)(iii) holds:

◊ If $G \setminus G_s$ is not empty, then by Theorem 2.3.(1).(ii), $\overline{G(x)} = \overline{\Lambda_G}(x - a) + E_G$ for some $a \in E_G$. Thus, $\dim(E_G) = n - 1$ and Λ_G must be dense in \mathbb{R} , so (b)(ii) holds.

◊ If $G = G_s$, then by Theorem 2.3.(2), $\overline{G(x)} = (x + \overline{G_t(0)}) \cup (-x + a + \overline{G_t(0)})$

for some $a \in \mathbb{R}^n$. In this case, Λ_G is bounded and $G_t(0)$ must be dense in \mathbb{R}^n , so (b)(iii) holds. \square

Proof of Theorem 2.5. If G is hypercyclic, then $\overline{G(x)} = \mathbb{R}^n$, for some $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, so $x \in U$. Let $y \in U \subset \overline{G(x)}$, then by Lemma 6.1, $\overline{G(y)} \cap U = \overline{G(x)} \cap U = U$. Since U is dense in \mathbb{R}^n , we get $\overline{G(y)} = \overline{G(x)} = \mathbb{R}^n$. The converse is obvious. \square

7. RATIONAL CRITERION FOR FINITELY GENERATED SUBGROUPS OF $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$

Proposition 7.1. *Let G be a finitely generated non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$, where $n \geq 2$. Then one of the following statements must be true:*

i) G is minimal and either G_s is nonempty or it is empty and $G_t(0)$ is dense in \mathbb{R}^n .

ii) G is minimal in a countable union of parallel vector subspaces of \mathbb{R}^n , and either $G \setminus G_s$ is nonempty or it is empty and $G_t(0)$ is not discrete and not dense in \mathbb{R}^n .

iii) Every orbit of G is closed and discrete, and in this case $G = G_s$. In addition, $G_t(0)$ is a discrete additive subgroup of \mathbb{R}^n .

Proof. Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. We analyze the structure of the closure of the orbits $\overline{G(x)}$ by considering the following cases:

Case 1: $G \setminus G_s \neq \emptyset$. That is, G contains elements outside the subgroup G_s . Then, by Remark 4.6, we have $\dim(E_G) \geq 1$. Moreover, by Theorem 2.3, we have:

$$\overline{G(x)} = \overline{\Lambda_G}(x - a) + E_G.$$

We distinguish the following subcases:

1) If $\dim(E_G) = n$, then $E_G = \mathbb{R}^n$, so $\overline{G(x)} = \mathbb{R}^n$, and assertion (i) follows.

2) If $\dim(E_G) < n - 1$, then:

- If $\overline{\Lambda_G} = \mathbb{R}$ and $x \in U$, then $\overline{G(x)}$ is an affine subspace of dimension less than n .
- If $\overline{\Lambda_G} \neq \mathbb{R}$, then $\overline{\Lambda_G}$ is discrete in $\mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$, so $\overline{G(x)}$ is a countable union of parallel affine subspaces in \mathbb{R}^n .

Hence, assertion (ii) holds.

3) If $\dim(E_G) = n - 1$ and $\overline{\Lambda_G} = \mathbb{R}$, then every orbit in U is dense in \mathbb{R}^n , leading to assertion (i) and for every $x \in E(G)$, $\overline{G(x)} = E_G$ and we get (ii).

4) If $\dim(E_G) = p = n - 1$ and $\overline{\Lambda_G} \neq \mathbb{R}$, then $\overline{\Lambda_G}$ is discrete in $\mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$, and we obtain assertion (ii).

Case 2: $G = G_s$, i.e., $G \subset \mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R})$. By Theorem 2.3, there exists $a \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, we have:

$$\overline{G(x)} = (x + \overline{G_t(0)}) \cup (-x + a + \overline{G_t(0)}).$$

We consider the following possibilities:

- If $G_t(0)$ is dense in \mathbb{R}^n , then each orbit of G is dense. This gives assertion (i).
- If $G_t(0)$ is a discrete additive subgroup of \mathbb{R}^n , then every orbit is discrete, giving assertion (ii).
- If $G_t(0)$ is a countable union of vector subspaces of \mathbb{R}^n , then so is every orbit. This proves assertion (iii).

□

For a non null real number λ , denote by:

$$- \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \lambda^k \mathbb{Z}^n = \left\{ \sum_{\substack{i \\ finite}} \lambda^{k_i} a, \quad k_i \in \mathbb{Z}, a \in \mathbb{Z}^n \right\}. \text{ the set of all finite sums of}$$

elements taken from the sets $\lambda^k \mathbb{Z}^n$, which is the additive group generated by all these sets.

Theorem 7.2. *Let $n \geq 1$. For any non null real number λ with $|\lambda| \neq 1$, the additive group $A_n(\lambda)$ generated by the set $\{\lambda^k a; k \in \mathbb{Z}, a \in \mathbb{Z}^n\}$ is dense in \mathbb{R}^n . This means that the group*

$$A_n(\lambda) = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \lambda^k \mathbb{Z}^n$$

is dense in \mathbb{R}^n .

Proof. Consider a non-abelian group G generated by the scaling transformation $h = \lambda \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}$ and the translations $T_{e_j} : x \mapsto x + e_j$ for $j = 1, \dots, n$, where

(e_1, \dots, e_n) is the standard basis of \mathbb{R}^n . The orbit of 0 under G is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
G(0) &= \left\{ \left(h^{k_1} \cdot T_{e_1}^{m_{1,1}} \dots T_{e_n}^{m_{n,1}} \right) \dots \left(h^{k_j} \cdot T_{e_1}^{m_{1,j}} \dots T_{e_n}^{m_{n,j}} \right) (0), \quad m_{i,t}, k_i \in \mathbb{Z}, j \in \mathbb{N} \right\} \\
&= \left\{ \lambda^{k_1} \left(\dots \left(\lambda^{k_j} \begin{bmatrix} m_{1,j} \\ \vdots \\ m_{n,j} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} m_{1,j-1} \\ \vdots \\ m_{n,j-1} \end{bmatrix} \right) + \dots \right) + \begin{bmatrix} m_{1,1} \\ \vdots \\ m_{n,1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{matrix} m_{i,j}, k_i \in \mathbb{Z}, \\ j \in \mathbb{N} \end{matrix} \right\} \\
&= \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^j \lambda^{k_1 + \dots + k_i} a_i; [k_1, \dots, k_j]^T \in \mathbb{Z}^j, a_1, \dots, a_j \in \mathbb{Z}^n, j \in \mathbb{N} \right\} \\
&= \left\{ \sum_{\substack{i \\ \text{finite}}} \lambda^{k_i} a_i, \quad k_i \in \mathbb{Z}, a_i \in \mathbb{Z}^n \right\} \\
&= A_n(\lambda)
\end{aligned}$$

According to Remark 4.6, the vector space E_G contains the canonical basis and, since $|\lambda| \neq 1$, we have that $E_G = \mathbb{R}^n$. Therefore, by Proposition 9.2, the set $G(0)$ is dense in \mathbb{R}^n . This means that the set $A_n(\lambda)$ is also dense in \mathbb{R}^n . \square

As a direct consequence, we can easily demonstrate the following result:

Corollary 7.3. *Any additive subgroup G of \mathbb{R} that includes the multiplicative group $\{\lambda^n; n \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ generated by a real number λ with $|\lambda| \neq 1$, is dense in \mathbb{R} .*

As a result, we can easily demonstrate the following example:

Example 7.4. The following additive groups are dense in \mathbb{R}^n ;

- i) $\sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} 2^k \mathbb{Z}^n$.
- ii) $\sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} 3^k \mathbb{Z}^n$.

Remark 7.5. All these sets can be seen as orbits under the action of a group finitely generated by homotheties.

Lemma 7.6. (cf. [18], page 35). *Let $F = \mathbb{Z}u_1 + \dots + \mathbb{Z}u_p$, where $u_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ for $k = 1, \dots, p$. Then the group F is dense in \mathbb{R}^n if and only if, for every $(s_1, \dots, s_p) \in \mathbb{Z}^p \setminus \{0\}$, the following condition is satisfied:*

$$\text{rank} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 & \dots & u_p \\ s_1 & \dots & s_p \end{bmatrix} = n + 1.$$

Lemma 7.7. (cf. [18], Corollary 1.4, page 18) Let Λ be a multiplicative subgroup of finite type of $\mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$. The following two conditions are equivalent:

- (i) Λ is dense in $\mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$.
- (ii) $\text{rank}_{\mathbb{Z}}(\Lambda) \geq 2$ and Λ contains a strictly negative real number.

7.1. G is generated by one dilation and a finite number of translations. In this section, we determine the form of the closure of $G_t(0)$ for a finitely generated non-abelian group G generated by affine homotheties.

Proposition 7.8. Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$ generated by a dilation $h = \lambda \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}$, with $\lambda \neq 1$, and p translations T_{a_1}, \dots, T_{a_p} , with respective translation vectors a_1, \dots, a_p . Then $G_t(0) = \sum_{k=1}^p \mathbb{Z} \Lambda_G a_k$.

Proof. In this case, G consists of homotheties and translations, and every dilation has a ratio of the form λ^m for some integer m . This means that $\Lambda_G = \{\lambda^m \mid m \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. Every element $f \in G$ has the form $f = h^{n_1} \circ T_{a_{i_1}}^{m_1} \dots h^{n_q} \circ T_{a_{i_q}}^{m_q}$, where $q \geq 2$, $i_k \in \{1, \dots, p\}$, and for $q = 1$, $f = h^k \circ T_{a_i}^m$ or $f = T_{a_i}^m \circ h^k$. However, if $f \in G_t$ and $q = 1$, then we have $f = h^k \circ T_{a_i}^m = T_{a_i}^m \circ h^k$,

$$\text{since } h = \lambda \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}. \text{ Let } H = \sum_{1 \leq k \leq p} \left(\sum_{m \in \mathbb{Z}} \lambda^m \mathbb{Z} a_k \right).$$

We will prove by induction on $q \geq 1$ that every $f \in G_t$ with the form $f = h^{n_1} \circ T_{a_{i_1}}^{m_1} \dots h^{n_q} \circ T_{a_{i_q}}^{m_q}$ satisfies $f(0) \in H$:

◦ For $q = 1$, $f = h^k \circ T_{a_i}^m$. Then $f(x) = h^k \circ T_{a_i}^m(x) = x + m a_i$, so $f(0) = m a_i \in H$.

◦ Suppose the property holds until rank q . Let $f = h^{n_1} \circ T_{a_{i_1}}^{m_1} \dots h^{n_{q+1}} \circ T_{a_{i_{q+1}}}^{m_{q+1}} \in G_t$. As f is a translation, it follows that $n_1 + \dots + n_{q+1} = 0$. Therefore, $f = f_1 \circ g$, where $f_1 = h^{n_1} \circ T_{a_{i_1}}^{m_1} \circ h^{-n_1}$ and $g = h^{n_1+n_2} \circ T_{a_{i_2}}^{m_2} \dots h^{n_{q+1}} \circ T_{a_{i_{q+1}}}^{m_{q+1}}$. It is clear that $g \in G_t$. By the induction hypothesis, we have $g(0) \in H$ and we can write $g(x) = x + b$, where $b \in H$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} h^{n_1} \circ T_{a_{i_1}}^{m_1} \circ h^{-n_1}(x) &= \lambda^{n_1} (\lambda^{-n_1} x + m_1 a_{i_1}) \\ &= x + \lambda^{n_1} m_1 a_{i_1} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$f(x) = f_1 \circ g(x) = f_1(x + b) = x + b + \lambda^{n_1} m_1 a_{i_1}$$

which implies that $f(0) = b + \lambda^{n_1} m_1 a_{i_1} \in H$.

◦ We conclude that $G_t(0)$ is included in H .

To finish the proof, we need to show that H is included in $G_t(0)$. To do this, we take $a = \sum_{i=1}^q \lambda^{m_i} n_{i_k} a_{i_k} \in H$ and consider the following element of G :

$$f = \left(h^{m_1} \circ T_{a_{i_1}}^{n_{i_1}} \circ h^{-m_1} \right) \circ \dots \circ \left(h^{m_q} \circ T_{a_{i_q}}^{n_{i_q}} \circ h^{-m_q} \right)$$

For each $1 \leq i \leq q$, we have

$$h^{m_k} \circ T_{a_{i_k}}^{n_{i_k}} \circ h^{-m_k}(x) = \lambda^{m_i} (\lambda^{-m_k} x + n_{i_k} a_{i_k}) = x + \lambda^{m_k} n_{i_k} a_{i_k}$$

Thus, $h^{m_k} \circ T_{a_{i_k}}^{n_{i_k}} \circ h^{-m_k}$ is a translation by the vector $\lambda^{m_k} n_{i_k} a_{i_k}$, and therefore, f is a translation by the vector $a = \sum_{k=1}^p \lambda^{m_i} n_{i_k} a_{i_k}$. This means that $f(0) = a \in G_t(0)$.

Therefore, H is included in $G_t(0)$. Since we have already shown that $G_t(0)$ is included in H , it follows that $G_t(0) = H = \sum_{k=1}^p \mathbb{Z} \Lambda_G a_k$. This completes the proof. \square

7.2. G is generated by a finite number of homotheties.

Lemma 7.9. *Let G be a group generated by $f_1 = (a_1, \lambda_1), \dots, f_p = (a_p, \lambda_p) \in \mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R}) \setminus \mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R})$ with $p \leq n$. Then $E_G := \sum_{k=2}^p \mathbb{R}(a_k - a_1) + a_1$. Moreover, $G_t(0) \subset \sum_{k=2}^p \mathbb{Z} \Lambda_G(a_k - a_1)$, which is dense in $E_G - a_1$.*

Proof. Firstly, we have $E_G - a_1$ is a vector space. Then $\sum_{k=2}^p \mathbb{R}(a_k - a_1)$ is

included in $E_G - a_1$. We will prove that $\sum_{k=2}^p \mathbb{R}(a_k - a_1)$ contains $C_s(G) - a_1$:

Let $f \in G \setminus G_t$, so $f = f_{i_1}^{n_1} \circ \dots \circ f_{i_q}^{n_q}$ for some $q \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $n_1, \dots, n_q \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $i_1, \dots, i_q \in \{1, \dots, p\}$. So for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= f_{i_1}^{n_1} \circ \dots \circ f_{i_q}^{n_q}(x) \\ &= \lambda_{i_1}^{n_1} (\lambda_{i_2}^{n_2} (\dots (\lambda_{i_{q-1}}^{n_{q-1}} (\lambda_{i_q}^{n_q} (x - a_{i_q}) + a_{i_q} - a_{i_{q-1}}) + a_{i_{q-1}} \dots) \dots - a_{i_1}) + a_{i_1} \\ &= \lambda_{i_1}^{n_1} \dots \lambda_{i_q}^{n_q} (x - a_{i_q}) + \sum_{k=1}^{q-1} \lambda_{i_1}^{n_1} \dots \lambda_{i_k}^{n_k} (a_{i_{k+1}} - a_{i_k}) + a_{i_1} \\ &= \lambda x + \sum_{k=1}^{q-1} \alpha_k (a_{i_{k+1}} - a_{i_k}) - \lambda (a_{i_q} - a_1) + (a_{i_1} - a_1) + (1 - \lambda) a_1 \end{aligned}$$

where $\lambda = \lambda_{i_1}^{n_1} \dots \lambda_{i_q}^{n_q}$ and $\alpha_k = \lambda_{i_1}^{n_1} \dots \lambda_{i_k}^{n_k}$. We define $f(x) = \lambda x + a$, where a is given by the equation

$$a = \sum_{k=1}^{q-1} \alpha_k (a_{i_{k+1}} - a_1) - \sum_{k=1}^{q-1} \alpha_k (a_{i_k} - a_1) - \lambda (a_{i_q} - a_1) + (a_{i_1} - a_1) + (1 - \lambda) a_1.$$

If f is not a translation, then $\lambda \neq 1$, and we can express f as $f = \left(\lambda, \frac{a}{1-\lambda} \right)$. From the form of a , we have

$$\frac{a}{1-\lambda} \in \sum_{k=2}^p \mathbb{R}(a_k - a_1) + a_1 \quad (1)$$

This implies that $C_s(G) \subset \sum_{k=2}^p \mathbb{R}(a_k - a_1) + a_1$, and therefore $E_G \subset \sum_{k=2}^p \mathbb{R}(a_k - a_1) + a_1$. If f is a translation, then $\lambda = 1$, and from equation (1) we get

$$f(0) = a = \sum_{k=1}^{q-1} \alpha_k (a_{i_{k+1}} - a_1) - \sum_{k=1}^{q-1} \alpha_k (a_{i_k} - a_1) - (a_{i_q} - a_1) + (a_{i_1} - a_1).$$

This quantity is contained in $\sum_{k=2}^p \mathbb{Z}\Lambda_G(a_k - a_1)$, which is dense in $E_G - a_1$. This follows from applying Lemma 4.3 on $G' = T_{-a_1} G T_{a_1}$ since $C_s(G')$ contains zero, so $\overline{G'_t(0)} = E_{G'}$. By Lemma 3.2, one has $E_{G'} = E_G - a_1$ and $G_t(0) = T_{-a_1}(G'_t(0))$, then $\overline{G_t(0)} = E_G - a_1$. The proof is completed. \square

Proposition 7.10. *The minimal number of dilations in $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R}) \setminus \mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R})$ that generate a non-abelian hypercyclic subgroup is $n - 1$.*

Proof. Let G be a group generated by $f_1 = (a_1, \lambda_1), \dots, f_{n-1} = (a_{n-1}, \lambda_{n-1})$ such that $\frac{\log|\lambda_1|}{\log|\lambda_2|} \notin \mathbb{Q}$ and a_1, \dots, a_{n-1} are free in $C_s(G)$. By Lemma 4.3.(ii), $\overline{C_s(G)} = E_G$, so the dimension of E_G is at least $n - 1$. On the other hand, $\overline{\Lambda_G} = \mathbb{R}$ since $\frac{\log|\lambda_1|}{\log|\lambda_2|} \notin \mathbb{Q}$. Therefore, by Theorem 2.4.(b), G is hypercyclic. Conversely, if G is a group generated by $f_1 = (a_1, \lambda_1), \dots, f_p = (a_p, \lambda_p) \in \mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R}) \setminus \mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R})$ with $p < n - 1$, then by Lemma 7.9, $E_G = \sum_{k=2}^p \mathbb{R}(a_k - a_1) + a_1$, so the dimension of E_G is at most $p < n - 1$. By Theorem 2.4, G cannot be hypercyclic. This completes the proof. \square

Proposition 7.11. *Let G be a non abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$ generated by $p + 1$ homotheties $f_0 = \lambda_0 \cdot \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}, f_1 = (\lambda_1, a_1) \dots, f_p = (\lambda_p, a_p)$ with centers at $0, a_1, \dots, a_p$ and non-unit scaling factors λ_i , and G_s is nonempty, then G is hypercyclic under one of the following two conditions:*

i) $\text{rank}(a_1, \dots, a_p) = n$.

ii) $\text{rank}_{\mathbb{Z}}(\Lambda_G) \geq 2$, there exists an i such that $\lambda_i < 0$, and $\text{rank}(a_1, \dots, a_p) = n - 1$.

Proof. The proof of this proposition follows from Theorem 2.4 part b), and Lemmas 7.9 and 7.7. \square

8. G IS A FINITELY GENERATED NON-ABELIAN SUBGROUP OF $\mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R})$

8.1. G is finitely generated by point symmetries.

Proposition 8.1. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{S}(n, \mathbb{R})$ generated by p symmetries S_1, \dots, S_p about points a_1, \dots, a_p , respectively. Then $G_t(0) = \sum_{k=2}^p 2\mathbb{Z}(a_k - a_1)$.*

Proof. In this case, note that G consists of point symmetries and translations. Since $S_i^2 = \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}$ for all i , every element f of G has the form $f = S_{i_1} \circ \dots \circ S_{i_q}$ for some positive integer q and $i_k \in \{1, \dots, p\}$. Denote $H = \sum_{k=2}^p 2\mathbb{Z}(a_k - a_1)$.

i) Firstly, let us prove by induction on $q \geq 1$ that every $f \in G_t$ with the form $f = S_{i_1} \circ \dots \circ S_{i_q}$ satisfies $f(0) \in H$:

◦ For $q = 1$, $f = \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}$ or $f = S_{i_k}^2 \in G_t$, so $f(0) = 0 \in H$.

◦ Suppose the property holds until rank q . Let $f = S_{i_1} \circ \dots \circ S_{i_{q+1}} \in G_t$. There are two cases:

- If $q + 1 = 2$, then $f = S_{i_1} \circ S_{i_2}$, which is a translation by the vector $2(a_{i_1} - a_{i_2})$, because

$$\begin{aligned} S_{i_1} \circ S_{i_2}(x) &= S_{i_1}(-(x - a_{i_2}) + a_{i_2}) = -(-(x - a_{i_2}) + a_{i_2} - a_{i_1}) + a_{i_1} \\ &= x + 2(a_{i_1} - a_{i_2}) \end{aligned}$$

which proves that $f(0) = 2(a_{i_1} - a_{i_2}) \in H$.

- If $q + 1 \geq 3$, let $g = S_{i_3} \circ \dots \circ S_{i_{q+1}}$. Then $f = S_{i_1} \circ S_{i_2} \circ g$. Since both f and $S_{i_1} \circ S_{i_2}$ are translations, then g must also be a translation. By the induction hypothesis, we have $g(0) \in H$ and write $g(x) = x + b$, where $b \in H$. By the above, we know that $S_{i_1} \circ S_{i_2}$ is a translation by the vector $2(a_{i_1} - a_{i_2})$, which implies that f is the composite of two translations and has a translation vector $f(0) = b + 2(a_{i_1} - a_{i_2}) \in H$.

◦ We conclude that $G_t(0)$ is included in H .

ii) Secondly, for the other inclusion, let $a = \sum_{k=1}^p 2n_k(a_k - a_1)$. On the other hand, for every $2 \leq k \leq p$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} S_k \circ S_1(x) &= -(-(x - a_1) + a_1 - a_k) + a_k \\ &= x + 2(a_k - a_1). \end{aligned}$$

Then $(S_k \circ S_1)^{n_k}(0) = 2n_k(a_k - a_1)$. Now we take $f = (S_2 \circ S_1)^{n_2} \circ \dots \circ (S_p \circ S_1)^{n_p}$, which is a translation with vector $a = \sum_{k=1}^p 2n_k(a_k - a_1)$ and so $f(0) = a \in G_t(0)$.

Therefore, $H \subset G_t(0)$, which completes the proof. \square

8.2. G is finitely generated by point symmetries and by translations.

Proposition 8.2. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$ generated by p point-symmetries $S_1 = (-1, a_1), \dots, S_p = (-1, a_p)$ and q translations T_{b_1}, \dots, T_{b_q} by the vectors b_1, \dots, b_q , then $G_t(0) = \sum_{k=1}^p 2\mathbb{Z}(a_k - a_1) + \sum_{k=1}^q \mathbb{Z}b_k$.*

Proof. In this case, every element f of G has the form

$$f = \left(S_{i_1}^{r_1} \circ T_{b_{j_1}}^{m_1} \right) \circ \dots \circ \left(S_{i_k}^{r_k} \circ T_{b_{j_k}}^{m_k} \right)$$

for some positive integer $k \geq 2$, $r_s \in \{0, 1\}$, $s = 1, \dots, k$, $i_k \in \{1, \dots, p\}$, $j_k \in \{1, \dots, q\}$, and for $k = 1$, either $f = S_{i_1}^{r_1} \circ T_{b_{j_1}}^{m_1}$ or $f = T_{b_{j_1}}^{m_1} \circ S_{i_1}^{r_1}$, with $r_1 \in \{0, 1\}$. However, if $f \in G_t$ and $k = 1$, we have $f = S_{i_1}^{r_1} \circ T_{b_{j_1}}^{m_1} = T_{b_{j_1}}^{m_1} \circ S_{i_1}^{r_1} = T_{b_{j_1}}^{m_1}$ and $r_1 = 0$. Let S_G denote the group generated by

$$S_1, \dots, S_p, \text{ and let } H := \sum_{k=1}^p 2\mathbb{Z}(a_k - a_1) + \sum_{k=1}^q \mathbb{Z}.b_k.$$

i) First step: We will prove, by induction on $k \geq 1$, that every element $f \in G_t$ of the form $f = \left(R_1 \circ T_{b_{j_1}}^{m_1} \right) \dots \left(R_k \circ T_{b_{j_k}}^{m_k} \right)$ with all $R_i \in S_G$, satisfies $f(0) \in H$.

Base case: when $k = 1$, we have $f = T_{a_{i_1}}^{m_1}$. Then $f(x) = T_{a_{i_1}}^{m_1}(x) = x + m_1 a_{i_1}$, so $f(0) = m_1 a_{i_1} \in H$.

Inductive case: Suppose the property holds for rank k . Let

$$f = \left(R_1 \circ T_{b_{j_1}}^{m_1} \right) \dots \left(R_{k+1} \circ T_{b_{j_{k+1}}}^{m_{k+1}} \right) \in G_t.$$

As f is a translation, it must be that the ratio of $R_1 \circ \dots \circ R_{k+1}$ equal 1. We distinguish two cases:

\diamond If $R_1 = id_{\mathbb{R}^n}$, then $f = g_1 \circ g$ with $g_1 = T_{a_{i_1}}^{m_1} \in G_t$ and $g = \left(S_{i_2}^{r_2} \circ T_{b_{j_2}}^{m_2} \right) \dots \left(S_{i_{k+1}}^{r_{k+1}} \circ T_{b_{j_{k+1}}}^{m_{k+1}} \right)$.

It is clear that $g \in G_t$. By the induction hypothesis, we have $g_1(0) = m_1 a_{i_1} \in H$ and $g(0) \in H$. Therefore, $f(0) = g_1(0) + g(0) \in H$.

\diamond If $R_1 = (-1, c)$, then $f = g_1 \circ g$ with $g_1 = R_1 T_{b_{i_1}}^{m_1} R_1$ and $g = R_1 \circ \left(R_2 \circ T_{b_{j_2}}^{m_2} \right) \dots R_{k+1} \circ T_{b_{j_{k+1}}}^{m_{k+1}} \in G_t$. Write

$$g = \left(R'_2 \circ T_{b_{j_2}}^{m_2} \right) \circ \left(R_3 \circ T_{b_{j_3}}^{m_{j_3}} \right) \circ \dots \circ \left(R_{k+1} \circ T_{b_{j_{k+1}}}^{m_{k+1}} \right) \quad \text{with } R'_2 = R_1 \circ R_2 \in S_G$$

then g has k factors in the form $(R_t \circ T_{b_{j_t}}^{m_t})$. By the induction hypothesis, we have $g(0) \in H$. On the other hand,

$$\begin{aligned} g_1(x) &= R_1 T_{b_{j_1}}^{m_1} R_1(x) \\ &= -(-(x-c) + c + m_1 b_{j_1} - c) + c \\ &= x - m_1 b_{j_1} \end{aligned}$$

Then $g_1(0) = -m_1 b_{j_1} \in H$ and so $f(0) = g_1(0) + g(0) \in H$. We conclude that every element in $G_t(0)$ is in H .

ii) Second step: We need to show that every element $a \in H$ can be written in the form $f(0)$ for some $f \in G_t$. To do this, we consider $a = \sum_{k=1}^p 2n_{i_k}(a_{i_k} -$

$$a_1) + \sum_{k=1}^q m_{j_k} b_{j_k} \in H, \text{ where } n_{i_k}, m_{j_k} \in \mathbb{Z}$$

By applying Proposition 8.1 on the group S_G , we have $(S_G)_t(0) = \sum_{k=1}^p 2\mathbb{Z}(a_{i_k} - a_1)$, where $(S_G)_t = S_G \cap G_t$. This means that there exists

a translation $T' \in G_t$ such that $T'(0) = \sum_{k=1}^p 2n_{i_k}(a_{i_k} - a_1)$.

Now, we consider the element $T = T_{b_{j_1}}^{m_{j_1}} \circ \dots \circ T_{b_{j_q}}^{m_{j_q}} \in G_t$. It follows that $T(0) = \sum_{k=1}^q m_{j_k} b_{j_k} \in H$.

Therefore, we can take $f = T' \circ T \in G_t$, which satisfies $f(0) = T'(0) + T(0) = a$. This completes the proof. \square

Proposition 8.3. *Let G be a non-abelian group generated by $p+1$ homotheties $f_0 = \lambda_0 \cdot \text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^n}$, $f_1 = (\lambda_1, a_1), \dots, f_p = (\lambda_p, a_p)$ of $\mathcal{D}(n, \mathbb{R})$. Then G is hypercyclic if and only if one of the following three assertions hold:*

- i) There exists $0 \leq i \leq p$ such that $|\lambda_i| \neq 1$ and $\text{rank}(a_1, \dots, a_p) = n$.*
- ii) $\text{rank}_{\mathbb{Z}}(\Lambda_G) \geq 2$, $\text{rank}(a_1, \dots, a_p) = n-1$, and there exists i such that $\lambda_i < 0$.*
- iii) $|\lambda_i| = 1$ for every $0 \leq i \leq p$, and for every $(s_1, \dots, s_{p+1}) \in \mathbb{Z}^{p+1} \setminus \{0\}$:*

$$\text{rank} \begin{bmatrix} 2a_{i_1} & \dots & 2a_{i_q} & a_{i_{q+1}} & \dots & a_{i_{p+1}} \\ s_1 & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & s_{p+1} \end{bmatrix} = n+1.$$

where $\lambda_{i_k} = -1$ for every $1 \leq k \leq q$ and $\lambda_{i_k} = 1$ for every $q+1 \leq k \leq p+1$.

Proof. The proof is divided into two cases.

\triangleright *Case 1:* If $G \setminus G_s \neq \emptyset$, then $|\lambda_i| \neq 1$ for some i . Assume that $|\lambda_0| \neq 1$ (leaving the possibility to take $T_{a_i} G T_{-a_i}$). Here E_G is a vector space because $C_s(G)$ contains zero. By Lemma 4.3.ii), $E_G = \overline{G_t(0)} = \overline{C_s(G)}$, which implies that all $a_i \in \overline{G_t(0)}$. There are two sub-cases:

- a) If $\text{rank}(a_1, \dots, a_p) = n$, then $E_G = \mathbb{R}^n$. By Theorem 2.4.b)i), G is hypercyclic, which gives us case i).
- b) If $\text{rank}(a_1, \dots, a_p) < n$, then E_G is a vector space with $\dim(E_G) \leq n - 1$. By Theorem 2.4.b)ii), G is hypercyclic if $\overline{\Lambda_G} = \mathbb{R}$ and $\dim(E_G) = n - 1$. Note that $\Lambda_G = \{\lambda_1^{n_1} \dots \lambda_p^{n_p}, n_i \in \mathbb{Z}\}$, and by Lemma 7.7, it is dense in \mathbb{R} if and only if $\text{rank}_{\mathbb{Z}}(\Lambda_G) \geq 2$ and there exists at least one i such that $\lambda_i < 0$, which gives us case ii).

▷ *Case 2:* If $G = G_s$, then $|\lambda_i| = 1$ for all $0 \leq i \leq p$. By Theorem 2.4.b)iii), G is hypercyclic if and only if $\overline{G_t(0)} = \mathbb{R}^n$. Let $\lambda_{i_k} = -1$ for all $1 \leq k \leq q$ and $\lambda_{j_k} = 1$ for all $q+1 \leq k \leq p+1$. Then by Proposition 8.2, $G_t(0) = \sum_{1 \leq k \leq q} 2\mathbb{Z}a_{i_k} + \sum_{q+1 \leq k \leq p+1} \mathbb{Z}a_{i_k}$. By Lemma 7.6, $G_t(0)$ is dense in \mathbb{R}^n if and only if for every $(s_1, \dots, s_{p+1}) \in \mathbb{Z}^{p+1} \setminus \{0\}$, the following matrix has rank $n + 1$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2a_{i_1} & \dots & 2a_{i_q} & a_{i_{q+1}} & \dots & a_{i_{p+1}} \\ s_1 & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & s_{p+1} \end{bmatrix}$$

This is case iii). □

9. CONSEQUENCES AND EXAMPLES IN DIMENSIONS $n \leq 2$

In this section, we will consider some consequences and examples of the results obtained in dimensions $n \leq 2$. Specifically, we will first discuss the consequences of our results in dimension $n = 1$, and then move on to examine examples in dimensions $n = 2$.

9.1. Consequences in dimension $n = 1$.

Proposition 9.1. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(1, \mathbb{R})$. Either of the following two conditions must hold:*

- i) G is minimal, meaning every orbit is hypercyclic. In this case, either $G \setminus G_s$ is nonempty or $G \setminus G_s$ is empty and $G_t(0)$ is dense in \mathbb{R} .
- ii) Every orbit of G is closed and discrete. In this case, G is a subgroup of translations-symmetries (i.e., $G = G_s$) and $G_t(0)$ is a discrete additive subgroup of \mathbb{R} .

Proof. Let G be a non abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(1, \mathbb{R})$. We consider two cases:
 i) If $G \setminus G_s$ is nonempty, then by Remark 4.6, $\dim E_G = 1$ and thus $E_G = \mathbb{R}$. From Theorem 2.4.b)i), we deduce that G is minimal (i.e., every orbit is hypercyclic).
 ii) If $G = G_s$, then by Theorem 2.3, there exists $a \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$\overline{G(x)} = \left(x + \overline{G_t(0)}\right) \cup \left(-x + a + \overline{G_t(0)}\right)$$

This implies that if $G_t(0)$ is a dense subset of \mathbb{R} , every orbit of G is hypercyclic. On the other hand, if $G_t(0)$ is a discrete additive subgroup of \mathbb{R} , every orbit of G is also discrete. \square

9.2. Consequences in dimension $n = 2$.

Proposition 9.2. *Let G be a non-abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(2, \mathbb{R})$. Then one of the following assertions is true:*

- (1) *Every orbit of G is hypercyclic. In this case, either $G \setminus G_s$ is nonempty or it is empty and $G_t(0)$ is dense in \mathbb{R}^2 .*
- (2) *Every orbit of G is dense in a countable union of parallel lines. In this case, either $(G \setminus G_s)$ is nonempty and $G_t(0)$ is dense in a line) or $(G \setminus G_s)$ is empty and $G_t(0)$ is not discrete and not dense in \mathbb{R}^2 .*
- (3) *Every orbit of G is closed and discrete. In this case, G is a subgroup of translations and point symmetries (i.e., it is contained in $\mathcal{S}(2, \mathbb{R})$) and $G_t(0)$ is a discrete additive subgroup of \mathbb{R}^2 .*

Proof. Let G be a non abelian subgroup of $\mathcal{D}(2, \mathbb{R})$. We consider the following two cases:

- i) If $G \setminus G_s$ is not empty, then by Remark 4.6, $\dim(E_G) \geq 1$.
 - a) If $\dim(E_G) = 2$, then $E_G = \mathbb{R}^2$ and we obtain the assertion (1) from Theorem 2.4.b)i).
 - b) If $\dim(E_G) = 1$, then E_G is a straight line in \mathbb{R}^2 and we get the assertion (2) from Theorem 2.4.b)ii).
- ii) If $G = G_s$, then by Theorem 2.3, there exists $a \in \mathbb{R}^2$ such that for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$,

$$\overline{G(x)} = \left(x + \overline{G_t(0)} \right) \cup \left(-x + a + \overline{G_t(0)} \right)$$

This implies that if $G_t(0)$ is dense in \mathbb{R}^2 , every orbit of G is hypercyclic. If $G_t(0)$ is a discrete additive subgroup of \mathbb{R}^2 , every orbit of G will be discrete as well, and we obtain the assertion (3) of the proposition. \square

Example 9.3. Let G be a subgroup of $\mathcal{S}(2, \mathbb{R})$ generated by the transformations $f_0 = -\text{id}_{\mathbb{R}^2}$, $f_1 = (-1, e_1)$, $f_2 = (-1, e_2)$ and $f_3 = (1, a_3)$, where $a_3 = [\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}]^T$ and (e_1, e_2) is the canonical basis of \mathbb{R}^2 . Then G is hypercyclic.

Proof. Let $(s_1, s_2, s_3) \in \mathbb{Z}^3 \setminus \{0\}$. Then we compute:

$$\Delta = \det \left(M_{(s_1, s_2, s_3)} \right) = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 0 & \sqrt{2} \\ 0 & 2 & \sqrt{3} \\ s_1 & s_2 & s_3 \end{vmatrix} = -2s_1\sqrt{2} - 2s_2\sqrt{3} + 4s_3.$$

Since 1, $\sqrt{2}$, and $\sqrt{3}$ are rationally independent, the determinant Δ is not equal to 0 for every $(s_1, s_2, s_3) \in \mathbb{Z}^3 \setminus \{0\}$. This implies that $\text{rank} \left(M_{(s_1, s_2, s_3)} \right) = 3$. By Theorem 8.3, we conclude that G is hypercyclic. \square

REFERENCES

1. H. Furstenberg, "Disjointness in Ergodic Theory, Minimal Sets, and a Problem in Diophantine Approximation," *Transactions of the American Mathematical Society*, vol. 123, no. 3, pp. 469-479, 1967.
2. J. Aaronson, *An Introduction to Infinite Ergodic Theory*, Mathematical Surveys and Monographs, vol. 50, American Mathematical Society, 1997.
3. P. Walters, *An Introduction to Ergodic Theory*, Graduate Texts in Mathematics, vol. 79, Springer, 2000.
4. V. D. Milman and L. T. Liptser, *Affine Differential Geometry and Its Applications*, Springer, 2015.
5. E. Hesseberg, *Geometry of Affine Spaces*, Springer, 1955.
6. L. Knox, *Affine Geometry: Geometry of Euclidean Space*, Cambridge University Press, 2017.
7. D. A. Forsyth and J. Ponce, *Computer Vision: A Modern Approach*, Prentice Hall, 2002.
8. P. Chou and S. Soatto, *Robot Vision and Image-Based Modeling*, Springer, 2005.
9. R. Hartley and A. Zisserman, *Multiple View Geometry in Computer Vision*, Cambridge University Press, 2003.
10. R. Murray, Z. Li, and S. Sastry, *A Mathematical Introduction to Robotic Manipulation*, CRC Press, 1994.
11. A. Ayadi, *Hypercyclic Abelian Groups of Affine Maps on C^n* , Canadian Mathematical Bulletin, doi, 10.4153, CMB-2012-019-6.
12. A. yadi, H. Marzougui and E. Salhi, *Hypercyclic abelian subgroups of $GL(n, R)$* , Journal of Difference Equations and Applications, 2011, 1–18.
13. M. Berger, *Geometry I*, Springer Berlin (1987), Series ISSN: 0172-5939.
14. Mohamed. J., *A generalization of Dirichlet approximation theorem for the affine actions on real line*, Journal of Number Theory 128 (2008) 1146–1156.
15. Salem, R. (1942). On transcendental numbers. *Mathematical Reviews*, **48**(2), 159.
16. Salem, R., & Newman, D. (1957). Some properties of the fractional parts of powers of algebraic numbers. *Transactions of the American Mathematical Society*, **85**(2), 377-396.
17. Vitaly. B, Michal. M and Samuel. S, *Affine actions of a free semigroup on the real line*, Ergod. Th. and Dynam. Sys. (2006), 26, 1285–1305.
18. Waldschmidt. M, *Topologie des points rationnels*, Cours de troisième Cycle, Université P. et M. Curie (Paris VI), 1994/95.

ADLENE AYADI, DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, FACULTY OF SCIENCES OF SFAX, SFAX, TUNISIA.

Email address: adlenesoo@yahoo.com

YAHIA N'DAO, DEPARTEMENT OF MATHEMATICS AND STATISTICS, UNIVERSITY OF MONCTON, CANADA

Email address: yahya.ndao@yahoo.ca

HAMED BEN YAHIA, DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, FACULTY OF SCIENCES OF GAFSA, GAFSA, TUNISIA.

Email address: hamed.benyahia@gmail.com